

Apéndice C

Relación de estudios seleccionados

Tabla C1

Relación de estudios seleccionados en la revisión

Año	Autor	Título del artículo	doi/url
2015	Ramírez-Fernández & Silvera	EDUTOOL®: Un instrumento para la evaluación y acreditación de la calidad de los MOOCs. Educación XX	https://www.redalyc.org/pdf/706/70638708004.pdf
2017	Torres et al.	Assessment of online learning at the Andalusian virtual campus: The case of Pablo Olavide University subjects. *InterCambios: Dilemas y Transiciones de la Educación Superior	https://0-dialnet-unirioja-es.llull.uib.es/servlet/extart?codigo=6064346
2020	Tobías et al.	Evaluación de la calidad en servicios de educación superior a distancia: Escala SERVQUAL y análisis factorial.	https://0-dialnet-unirioja-es.llull.uib.es/servlet/extart?codigo=7656736
2017	Sujono & Santoso	E-learning quality analysis of use of web conference in the improvement of students with learning method WebQual (Case study: Universitas KH. A. Wahab Hasbullah).	https://www.proquest.com/scholarly-journals/e-learning-quality-analysis-use-web-conference/docview/1890051876/se-2?accountid=29068
2019	Alizadeh et al.	Evaluating a blended course for Japanese learners of English: Why quality matters	https://doi.org/10.1186/s41239-019-0137-2

2015	Martínez et al.	An application of the performance-evaluation model for e-learning quality in higher education.	https://www.proquest.com/scholarly-journals/application-performance-evaluation-model-e/docview/1669844557/se-2?accountid=29068
2020	Muhammad et al.	A hierarchical model to evaluate the quality of web-based e-learning systems.	https://doi.org/10.3390/su12104071
2011	Alkhatabi et al.	Assessing information quality of e-learning systems: A web mining approach. Web 2.0 in Travel and Tourism: Empowering and Changing the Role of Travelers	https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chb.2010.11.011
2022	Saleh et al.	The evaluation of user experience of learning management systems using UEQ	https://doi.org/10.3991/ijet.v17i07.29525
2021	Su	Research of online course quality evaluation system by AHP entropy algorithm and weight coefficient.	https://doi.org/10.1109/AEECA52519.2021.9574212
2021	Liu et al.	The study of quality evaluation model for the real-time interactive online teaching	https://doi.org/10.1109/ICEIT51700.2021.9375621
2021	Tang et al.	Quality evaluation of online courses during COVID-19 pandemic based on integrated FCE-AHP method	https://doi.org/10.3233/JIFS-210362
2020	Beiqing & Chunrong	Design of online teaching quality evaluation system for Private University: - Research based on deep learning algorithm	https://doi.org/10.1109/ICMEIM51375.2020.00015
2019	Choi & Jeong	Quality evaluation for multimedia contents of e-learning systems using the ANP approach on high-speed network.	https://doi.org/10.1007/s11042-019-7351-8
2017	Balyk et al.	Development of e-Learning quality assessment model in Pedagogical University	https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85020533433&partnerID=40&md5=8f7ec0ec12b1ff11b62e9da06314761d

2014	Vila et al.	Assessment of the pedagogical quality of the MOOC.	https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-84903763155&partnerID=40&md5=c6e6e9e2b0a36f506df7c4cde2dd4773
2021	Schijns	Measuring service quality at an online university: Using PLS-SEM with archival data	https://doi.org/10.1007/s11233-021-09071-7
2008	Hay et al.	Measuring the quality of e-learning.	https://search.ebscohost.com/login.aspx?direct=true&db=asn&AN=34805549&lang=es&site=ehost-live
2024	Li	A construction of online teaching quality evaluation model based on big data mining	https://doi.org/10.1504/ijceell.2024.135271
2023	Theresiawati et al.	Implementing quality function deployment using service quality and Kano model to the quality of e-learning.	https://doi.org/10.11591/ijere.v12i3.25511
2022	Esmaeili et al.	Quality assessment of E-learning website using asymmetric impact–performance analysis and Kano’s customer satisfaction model: A case study based on WebQual 4.0.	https://doi.org/10.1108/IDD-08-2021-0083
2023	Zhang & Liu	Online teaching quality evaluation: Entropy TOPSIS and grouped regression model.	https://doi.org/10.3991/ijet.v18i16.41353
2023	Zhou & Zhang	Evaluation method of online education quality based on fuzzy rough set	https://doi.org/10.1504/ijceell.2023.132419
2023	Hou	The method of online classroom teaching quality evaluation based on deep data mining.	https://doi.org/10.1504/ijceell.2023.132388
2023	Li	A model for assessing the quality of a distance education programme in an online environment: China’s experience	https://doi.org/10.15516/cje.v25i1.4568
2022	Ramírez et al.	La calidad de la docencia online en la educación superior: Un nuevo enfoque para su medición	https://doi.org/10.15366/reice2022.20.3.005

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Student's satisfaction of the quality of online learning in higher education: An empirical study.

<https://doi.org/10.3390/su132111960>
